

Geophysical investigation of groundwater potential using vertical electrical sounding at a West African location

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ABSTRACT

The determination of groundwater potential using vertical electrical sounding (VES) was carried out at the undeveloped site of a West African location at the federal university of Wukari in Taraba State of Nigeria. The research is aimed at delineating groundwater potential and identification of a suitable site for the drilling of a productive motorized borehole in the grounds of the university. The measurement was conducted using a terrameter SAS 300C. The collected data were analyzed using IP12WIN and surfer version 7.0 software. The geographical location of the area is bounded by latitude 7.015°N to 7.850°N and longitude 9.047°E to 9.783°E. Three to four main geological layers were identified from the geo-electric characteristics of the area, which comprises of fine soil and clay sand of topsoil, soft shale weathered and fractured sand stone. Layer's thickness ranges from 1.4-3.0m for topsoil, 3.0-5.0m for fine sand, 5-10m for clay sand. The results of the interpreted VES data showed that the saturated groundwater bearing layer (aquifer) lie within the weathered and fractured sand stone of the predominantly four-layered geo-electric structure. The inferred areas for groundwater accumulation were found to be VES1, VES3, VES7, VES8, and VES9. The research concludes that these areas form the best sites for drilling boreholes.

Keywords Borehole, Electrical sounding, Geological layers, Groundwater potential, Lithology

1. Introduction

Water in any society is of paramount importance, the need and use of water by man, plant and animals is universal [1]. Noted that it is interesting that there is hardly enough water to drink and meet other basic requirement such as cooking, washing and bathing among other usage in most communities of developing nations. The easiest and most convenient way to meet the public demand for water is to utilize the surface water resources. Unfortunately, rivers, streams and lakes may exist in some areas and may not exist in others, or may dry up in the dry season. Full and proper management is desired and necessary for social stability and even human survival. Large water supply of such commodities also widens. The full and proper development of our water resources becomes inevitable despite its complications and expenses [2]. Therefore surmises that there is need for sustainable underground water development and utilization. Prolonged in-situ weathering of the crystalline basement complex rocks under tropical conditions has produced a sequence of unconsolidated material whose thickness and lateral extent vary extensively. The localization of groundwater within these zones is controlled by a number of factors which include the parent rock type, the depth, extent and pattern of weathering, thickness of the weathered materials, the sand/clay ratio and the degree of fracturing, fissuring and jointing [3].

Groundwater exploration employs a varieties of techniques in which the most widely used are electrical resistivity, seismic refraction and electromagnetic methods. Electrical resistivity method is commonly used because it is efficient, cheap and also gives valuable information about the aquifer potential. Resistivity method operates by employing an artificial source of current, which is introduced into the subsurface using resistivity setup. Electrical sounding gives information on water bearing structures and easily determine the vertical variation of the earth electrical properties which can be related to the geology of the area.

2. Location of the study area

The study area hosts the permanent site of Federal University Wukari and lies between latitude 7.015°N to 7.850°N and longitude 9.047°E to 9.783°E. The site is situated along a road leading to a town called Katsina Ala, a rural settlement in the middle belt of Nigeria.

2.1. Topography

The topography of the study area is that of high plain (flat terrain) of a designated Jukun land in Wukari that has a climate, which is classified as tropical with average annual temperature of 26.4°C (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Map of Wukari LGA Taraba State Nigeria.

2.2. Weathering

Like most parts of northern Nigeria, Taraba State has a wet and dry climate. The wet season lasts on the average from April to October. Mean annual rainfall varies between 1058mm in the north around Jalingo and Zing, to over 1300mm in the south around Takum and Wukari areas. The wettest months are August and September. The dry season lasts from November to March. The driest months are December and January with relative humidity dropping to about 15%. Mean annual temperature around Jalingo is about 28°C with maximum temperatures varying between 30°C and 39.4°C. The minimum temperatures range between 15°C to 23°C. The region is situated in the same location as the mambilla plateau, which has climatic characteristics typical of a temperate climate. This impact on temperatures is low throughout the year and the rainy season lasts from February to November with a mean annual rainfall of over 1850mm [4].

3. Methodology

The investigation of the target area was carried out using VES of electrical resistivity method. This method is designed to detect the physical and structural characteristics of the basement rocks such as variation in conductivity. In the DC resistivity surveying, an electric current is passed into the ground through two outer electrodes (A and B), and the resultant potential difference is measured across two inner electrodes (M and N) that are arranged in a straight line,

symmetrically about a centre point as shown in Figure 2. The ratio of the potential difference to the current is displayed by the terrametera resistance. A geometric factor in meters is calculated as a function of the electrode spacing. The electrode spacing is progressively increased, keeping the center point of the electrode array fixed. Terrameter signal averaging system (SAS) model 300C was the instrument used. No booster was used as the expected depth is within the range of penetration of the instrument.

Figure 2 Investigation of the target area by using VES of electrical resistivity.

A and B are current electrodes through which current is supplied into the ground, M and N are two potential electrodes to measure the potential differences between the two electrodes and P is the VES station. The potential difference between the two potential electrodes is measured. The apparent resistivity is given by $\rho_a = K (\Delta V/I)$ with K a geometric factor which only depends on electrode spacing. The apparent resistivity measurements give information about resistivity for a medium whose volume is proportional to the electrode spacing [5]. Resistivity is affected more by water content and quality than the actual rock material in porous formations [6]. While aquifers that are composed of unconsolidated materials their resistivity decreases with the degree of saturation and salinity of the groundwater [7].

The terrameter was switch ON reading was taking, thereafter the terrameter was switch OFF, The current electrodes were expanded simultaneously in opposite side of VES point, reading was taking at each new point until a distance of 68m was covered. The potential electrodes remain fixed at 0.2m and as the distance between the current electrodes get too large, and then the potential electrode was expanded from 1.0m, 1.45m up to 6.80m. Lastly the equipment’s were moved to the other VES point, until the whole distance was covered. The coordinate, elevation and azimuth of each VES point were taken using global positioning system (GPS) machine.

3.1. Data analysis

The apparent resistivity data are presented as sounding curves, these curves are then obtain by plotting the apparent resistivity values against half of the corresponding current electrodes separation (AB/2). The curve type in each VES station depends on the subsurface layer sequence as shown in Figure 3. Where, N=layer number, h=thickness (m), ρ =resistivity (Ωm), d=depth to the bottom (m) and Alt=altitude (m). The summary of the result for all the sounding points VES as given in Table 1.

Figure 3 VES curves and model data.

4. Results

Figure 4 is the geoelectric and geologic section of profile 01. The profile is 2m away from the road leading to the staff quarters building, 5m away from water fountain roundabout and south eastern to the school main gate. The profile is underlain by three to four subsurface layers. The first layer is interpreted as top soil with thickness range between 2.0m

to 3.0m. The second layer is mainly fine sand with resistivity values of 145Ωm to 246Ωm. The third layer along the profile is inferred to be dominated by clay/soft shale except around VES 02 to 03 that is dominated by sandstone formation. Hence this area form one of the best sides for drilling bore hole.

S/N	VES	1 st Layer			2 nd Layer			3 rd Layer			4 th Layer			Curve type
		Resistivity (Ωm)	Thickness(m)	Depth(m)										
1	VES1	175	02	0.2	202	05	02	18	08	07	73	∞	15	QA
2	VES2	128	02	0.1	246	05	02	250	07	04	25	∞	14	HQ
3	VES3	407	1.4	0.5	145	04	1.4	42	10	3.4	12	13	13.4	Q
4	VES4	257	02	0.1	47	03	02	407	02	05	53	12	07	A
5	VES5	127	03	0.2	325	02	02	61	05	05	359	03	10	KQ
6	VES6	217	02	0.1	307	04	02	321	0.1	06	334	08	08	H
7	VES7	223	03	0.1	76	06	03	38	31	11	26	0.2	42	Q
8	VES8	419	02	0.1	17	03	02	70	40	05	22	0.1	45	K
9	VES9	138	02	0.2	73	04	02	11	06	06	168	0.2	12	AQ
10	VES10	180	03	0.1	15	18	03	2648	0.5	31	3472	∞	-40	A
11	VES11	113	03	0.2	231	04	03	28	04	07	6388	0.5	20	AQ

Table 1 Summary of the result for all the sounding points VES.

Figure 4 Goelectric and geological section of profile 01.

4.1. Goelectrical and geological section of profile three

Figure 5 is the goelectric and geologic section of profile 03. Profile 03 runs approximately north-east of the main gate, in front of new information communication technology (ICT) building. It is dominated by four subsurface layers with first layer interpreted as top soil with resistivity value ranging between 113Ωm to 180Ωm and the thickness of the layer

range between of 2m to 3m. The second layer is mainly clay/soft-shale with resistivity values of $15\Omega\text{m}$ to $25\Omega\text{m}$. The third layer along the profile is inferred to be dominated by sandy shale with average thickness of 18m to 20m. VES point 09 and 011 is also recommended as suitable for groundwater exploitation; beneath this layer could be sandstone. Consequently this area is not recommended for dumping refuse due to the filtering nature of the top soil which can easily contaminate the ground water.

Figure 5 Geoelectric and geological section of profile 03.

4.2. Discussion

The modeling of the VES measurements carried out at eleven (11) stations has been used to derive the geoelectric sections for the various profiles. These have revealed that there are mostly three and four geologic layers beneath each VES station. The geologic sequence beneath the study area is composed of topsoil, soft shale and sand stone. The topsoil is composed of fine soil, sandy-clay and sandy-lateritic hard crust with resistivity values ranging from $25\Omega\text{m}$ to $419\Omega\text{m}$ and thickness varying from 1.4 to 3.0m. It is however, observed from the geoelectric sections that VES 1, 3, 7, 8 and 9 are characterized with low resistivity values suggesting the clayey nature of the topsoil in the area, hence possibly high moisture content and therefore shall be recommended for drilling boreholes.

5. Conclusion

A complete evaluation of a hydrogeological unit comprises of the availability, productivity and quality of the groundwater within the study area. The research provides guidance for drilling schedules and continuity for understanding the surface disposition of the shallow aquifer systems and useful guide for more elaborate groundwater development in the area. The inferred areas for groundwater accumulation were found to be VES1, VES3, VES7, VES8, and VES9. The research concludes that these areas form the best sites for drilling boreholes.

The agreement of the interpretation of sounding data with geological information's gives an indication that the present study in the determination of groundwater potential. It is thus recommended that for appreciable volume of water to be pumped, boreholes should be constructed at VES 1, VES 3, VES 7, VES 8, and VES 9. The borehole drilling can be terminated at depth of 10m. The maximum profile length of AB = 45m. Further studies should be carried out to delineate the deeper aquifer and the coverage should be expanded to include all the areas in the university.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interest.

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